

Data from “Elastic Displacement of the Solid Earth and GRACE/GRACE-FO Response to Variations in Global Lake and Reservoir Storage”

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Overview

This product contains the data produced by the study “Elastic Displacement of the Solid Earth and GRACE/GRACE-FO Response to Variations in Global Lake and Reservoir Storage” by Gaastra et al. 2025. This data describes the effect of changes in lake water storage in 983 global natural lakes and man-made reservoirs from October 1992 to October 2020 on the mass change estimates of the GRACE/GRACE-FO satellite missions and the elastic displacement of the solid Earth at GNSS stations recorded by the Nevada Geodetic Laboratory. We report the lake water storage timeseries, our maps of lake water storage change through time on a 0.1-degree grid, our predictions for GRACE mass change, and east, north, and up displacements at GNSS stations with uncertainties.

This data set contains:

- 1) Interpolated timeseries of lake water storage for 983 global lakes and reservoirs (directory: 1_LWSTimeseries)
 - a. Shape files of the 983 lakes that were included in this study (file: GLWS_Lakes_included.shp)
 - b. Shape files of the lakes that were excluded from this study but which were in the Global Lake Water Storage data set (Yao et al. 2023) (file: GLWS_Lakes_excluded.shp)
 - c. Ascii text file for each lake containing the continuous monthly lake water storage and its 1-sigma uncertainty in units of km^3 from October 1992 to October 2020. An interpolation flag is provided to indicate which months are interpolated. (files: ID\$LAKEID_\$LAKENAME.txt)
- 2) Maps of monthly lake water globally in those 938 lakes and reservoirs (directory: 2_LWSMaps)
 - a. A netCDF file containing liquid water equivalent values relative to January 1st, 2014 in a 0.1-degree global grid of all the lakes and reservoirs in this study from October 1992 to October 2020 with their uncertainties, an interpolation mask, and a map of the percent lake water area in each grid cell (file: Global_Yao2023_983Lakes_10deg.nc)
- 3) Maps of contribution of lake water storage change to estimates of GRACE terrestrial water storage change (directory: 3_GRACEMaps)

- a. A netCDF file containing lake water storage change relative to January 1st, 2014 in each JPL-GRACE 3-degree mass concentration unit (mascon) from April 2002 to October 2020 with values placed on a 0.5-degree regular grid (file: LWS_mascon_grid.nc)
 - b. A netCDF file containing estimates of lake water storage change relative to January 1st, 2014 smoothed by a 334 km Gaussian filter for comparison to GRACE spherical harmonic estimates of mass change evaluated at points on a 0.5-degree regular grid (file: LWS_smoothed_grid.nc)
 - c. Spherical harmonic coefficients in GSM format for each month from April 2002 to October 2020 to degree and order 120 recording lake water storage change relative to January 1st, 2014 after smoothing by a 334 km Gaussian filter (directory: sh_coef)
- 4) Files for each of the 21,229 stations recorded by the Nevada Geodetic Laboratory as of July 2024 with predictions of displacements due to changes in lake water storage loading the surface of the Earth in the 983 lakes studied (directory: 4_GNSSPositions; Note: only 19,827 of these stations have a record during the interval October 1992 to October 2020, but the prediction of lake water loading at their location prior to their installation is provided for completeness)
- a. Each file contains decimal year and east, north, and up displacements in units of meters with their 1-sigma uncertainties for the station in the file name (files: \$STATIONNAME.enu)